

ISic1283

I.Sicily inscription 1283

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

terracotta

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

4.2006

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140773

1. ΚΤΙ[— — —]ΤΑΣ

2. Ἄρτ[εμίδωρ]ος Τ

3. [— — — — — — —]

4.

Edition: PHI316194

1. [— — —]ΚΤΙ [— — —]

2. [— — —]ΑΡΤ [— — —]

3.

4. [— — —]ΤΑΣ [— — —]

5. [— — —]ΟΣΤ [— — —]

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492888

EDCS 39101652

PHI 140773

PHI 316194

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0459 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 3

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5732e (fr.a only)

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1283. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385750>